

Protoberberine Alkaloids*

T. R. GOVINDACHARI**

I am greatly honoured for having been asked to deliver the Acharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial lecture.

Acharya Ghosh was one of India's great scientists who laid the foundations for scientific research and education in our country. We of the present generation owe a debt of gratitude to Acharya Ghosh for his great service in the cause of science.

The protoberberines are an interesting group of alkaloids which commonly occur in plants belonging to the *Berberidaceae*, *Ranunculaceae*, *Menispermaceae* and *Rutaceae*. The first alkaloid of the series berberine was isolated in 1837 from *Berberis vulgaris* and now over one hundred alkaloids are known. The alkaloids occur both in the form of quaternary salts with the skeletal structure I or as tertiary bases of type II.

There are several excellent reviews of protoberberine chemistry¹⁻⁴. In this lecture attention will be confined mainly to some interesting contributions made from Presidency College, Madras, in the field of protoberberine chemistry.

Synthetic studies :

The alkaloid ophiocarpine(III) is unusual in that, it carries an alcoholic hydroxyl group at C₁₃. Its synthesis was effected as depicted in Scheme I⁶ based on a synthetic route devised by Perkin *et al*⁶.

Chart -1

The meconin carboxylic acid needed in the synthesis was easily made from opianic acid obtained by oxidation from narcotine, the most abundant alkaloid of opium. The diastereoisomeric mixture of dl-ophiocarpine and dl-epi-ophiocarpine was separated and the former resolved yielding l-ophiocarpine identical with the natural product.

Hydrogenolysis of d-ophiocarpine yields l-tetrahydroberberine, establishing the configuration at C₁₄ as (R)⁷. Since both ophiocarpine and epiophiocarpine show Bohlmann bands, both should have a trans-quinolizidine ring system. Ophiocarpine has OH absorption in the infrared, characteristic of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding, possible only if the OH is axial. This leads to the absolute configuration depicted in III⁷.

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** Director, Research & Development, Amrutnjan Ltd, Madras-4

The benzylic hydroxyl at C₁₃ is easily removed by hydrogenolysis. The route depicted in Chart I was employed for the syntheses of dl-capaurimine (IV)⁸, as well as for the phenolic alkaloids corypalmine(V) and isocorypalmine(VI)⁹. The last step was a reduction effected with a Pd catalyst in the presence of perchloric acid.

The method can be used for a large number of protoberberine alkaloids, most of which carry methoxyl groups at C₉ and C₁₀. Since meconin carboxylic acid is easily available, this route is quite practical, contrary to the statement of Shamma¹⁰. An important route to the synthesis of the protoberberine skeleton is the Mannich cyclisation of a 1-benzyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline. Mannich cyclisation with formaldehyde of 1-(3', 4'-dimethoxybenzyl)-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro-6,7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline(VII) leads to the formation of tetrahydro-ψ-berberine(VIII).

Since a vast majority of protoberberines are substituted in the 9,10-position, the method as such is limited in scope since it leads essentially to the 10, 11-oxygenated compounds. In order to force the cyclisation to take place at the 2'-position, bromine was used as the blocking group. Haworth and Perkin found however that the Mannich reaction did not at all proceed with the bromo compound IX¹¹. However, the N-formyl derivative underwent cyclisation, giving only the ψ-berberine VIII. The authors remark that the tendency of cyclisation to the *para* position to the methoxy substituent was so great that the bromine was ejected.

A reinvestigation of the route employing bromine as a blocking group was considered desirable and it was first tested in the synthesis of dl-tetrahydrogröenlandicine¹². Cyclisation of the bromoamide XII with POCl₃ yielded the protoberberine XIII

found to be a mixture of chloro and bromo compounds. This was indicated by the presence in the mass spectrum of peaks at m/e 405 and 403 (bromo compound) and 361 and 359 (chloro compound). Reductive cleavage of the halogen with 10% Pd/C in ethanol followed by debenzoylation yielded dl-tetrahydrogröenlandicine(XV). The cyclisation product with the bromine ejected(XIV) was found to be the major compound (3 : 1).

By a similar procedure, with appropriate starting materials, the synthesis of dl-stepholidine(XVI) was achieved¹³. With the use of POCl₃, halogen exchange prevailed, the product of cyclisation being one in which the bromine had been replaced significantly by chlorine(XVII). It was however possible to reduce XVII to the desired tetrahydroprotoberberine XVI. The 10, 11-oxygenated compound,

arising from displacement of bromine was also formed in considerable yield. In a reinvestigation of the work of Haworth and Perkin (*loc cit*) the bromoamide X was cyclised with POCl₃, followed by reduction with NaBH₄ to yield 12-chlorocanadine(XI). But attempts at replacement of chlorine by hydrogen failed. In order to avoid the halogen exchange, POBr₃ was used as a cyclising agent and after NaBH₄ reduction, 12-bromocanadine was obtained, which was hydrogenolysed to yield dl-canadine.

The major product in the POBr₃ cyclisation was however one in which the bromine had been ejected to give a 10, 11-oxygenated protoberberine. Using POBr₃ as a cyclising agent, it was possible to

accomplish syntheses of dl-sinactine(XVIII) and dl-stylophine(XIX)¹⁴. Perhaps, subtle factors such

as the pattern of oxygen substitution or purity of the phosphorus oxychloride are at play in the cyclisation reaction, since Tani *et al*¹⁵ succeeded in cyclising a bromoamide with POCl₃ without halogen exchange and obtained finally dl-cheilanthalifoline.

Synthesis of Thalictrifoline :

The alkaloid thalictrifoline(XX) is unique in being the only naturally occurring 13-methyltetrahydroprotoberberine, with the B/C ring having a *cis*-quinolizidine conformation. Its C₁₃ epimer, base II (Cavidine) (XXI) also occurs naturally and has been shown to have a B/C *trans*-junction.

The synthesis outlined in Chart 2 is based on that of Shamma¹⁶ for 13-methyltetrahydro- ψ -protoberberine with a modification involving the use of a

Chart—2

bromine as a blocking group to achieve a 9,10-oxygenation pattern. The dihydroisoquinoline indicated in the scheme was easily prepared. Reduction yielded only one diastereoisomer, XXII which was shown to be the *erythro*-compound as indicated by the chemical shift of the C-methyl group (δ 1.23). The tetrahydroisoquinoline on being heated with formaldehyde and acid under a variety of conditions did not yield the expected tetrahydroprotoberberine, but a product, m.p. 210° to which structure XXIII has been assigned on the basis of extensive spectral data and degradation

studies¹⁷. The structure has been confirmed by an X-ray crystallographic study¹⁸ which has also revealed the relative stereochemistry. The formation of structure XXIII has been rationalised in terms of the reaction mechanism depicted in Chart 3.

Chart -3

Not being succeeded in achieving a Mannich cyclisation, attention was turned to the N-formyl derivative(XXIV). This was submitted to the Bischler-Napieralsky reaction under a variety of conditions. It was found that with both POCl₃ and POBr₃, the bromine atom was ejected giving

a 10, 11-oxygenated product, which was reduced with NaBH_4 to a mixture of C_{13} methyl epimers. When an undistilled sample of POBr_3 was used a bromo compound was obtained in poor yield. The yield of the bromo compound was improved by using a mixture of PBr_5 and P_2O_5 ¹⁹. After reduction of the crude product with NaBH_4 , four products were isolated, two of which were identical with the bromine-free C_{13} -methyl epimers, belonging to the pseudotetrahydroprotoberberine series (10, 11-oxygenated). The two bromine-containing compounds gave the same two epimers on reductive debromination. It was therefore clear that the cyclisation of the bromoamide (XXV) has only been accomplished at the site of the bromine atom after its expulsion, followed by nuclear bromination.

The structures of these two compounds were assigned as XXV and XXVI on the basis of NMR and mass spectral data¹⁹. The compound m.p. 146°

had an R_f ($\text{CHCl}_3 : \text{MeOH} : \text{EtOAc } 40 : 1 : 2.5$) of 0.9, rate of methiodide formation $1.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S}^{-1}$ (31.5°), a methyl doublet in the NMR ($J=7\text{Hz}$) at $\delta 0.93$ corresponding to the C_{13} -methyl group and a broad singlet and $\delta 3.75$ (C_8H). The other compound m.p. 160° had an R_f 0.5, rate of methiodide formation $99.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S}^{-1}$, a methyl doublet at $\delta 1.47$ ($J=7\text{Hz}$) and an AB quartet at $\delta 3.71$ ($J=16\text{Hz}$) and $\delta 4.16$ ($J=16\text{Hz}$) corresponding to the methylene at C_8 . On the basis of this evidence, the former was assigned the *trans*-quinolizidine structure XXV and the latter the *cis*-quinolizidine structure XXVI. The mass spectra of both compounds showed typical fragmentation characteristic of tetrahydroprotoberberines as shown in Chart 4. This indicated that the bromine was in ring A. It was considered likely to be in position 4.

However, there was no easy way of proving this by chemical degradation. A pair of compounds similar to the two compounds discussed above were obtained from the amide XXVII. These were assigned the structures XXVIII and XXIX on the basis of NMR spectra and other physical data. X-ray crystallographic analysis of the two compounds were carried out by Prof. Rogers at the Imperial College, London²⁰.

X-ray analysis of the compound, m.p. 205-206°, assigned the *trans*-quinolizidine structure revealed that the bromine was in position 4. But there was evidence that some 4 per cent of the molecules carry bromine at C_9 as well as for minor amounts of a 4, 9-dibromo compound. The transference of the quinolizidine viz. XXVIII assigned¹⁹ on the basis of physical data was fully confirmed.

X-ray analysis of the compound m.p. 179° confirmed the presence of a *cis*-quinolizidine system (XXIX) and the presence of bromine at position 4. These X-ray studies constitute the first example of such a study on a pair of epimeric 13-methyl tetrahydroprotoberberines and help to give credence to the conclusions on B/C-ring geometry based hitherto on NMR and other physical data.

The synthesis of dl-thalictrifoline and dl-cavidine was finally accomplished by the route shown in Chart 5²¹. The route is based on a procedure developed by Cushman *et al*²².

Stereochemical aspects of tetrahydroprotoberberines :

It has been well established that all tetrahydroprotoberberines with a negative rotation have a 14 R configuration²³. However, this can be applied only to compounds unsubstituted at C₁₃ and C₈ with confidence.

The tetrahydroprotoberberines are dibenzo-(a,g)-quinolizidines and due to the conformational mobility of the nitrogen atom, it is possible to write one *trans*-quinolizidine and two *cis*-quinolizidine conformations for any structure. It is assumed that the two rings (B and C) have a quasi-chair conformation. These are depicted in Chart 6. The actual

Chart-6

conformation of a compound is decided by the nature of the substitution at position 1, 8 or 13. In compounds unsubstituted at these positions the *trans*-quinolizidine conformation will prevail, being thermodynamically, the most stable. Generally, such compounds display in the IR spectra prominent peaks in the 2700-2800 cm⁻¹ region, named the Bohlmann bands. Kessar has pointed out that the Bohlmann bands can only detect the *trans*-fused conformation and cannot rule out the presence of substantial quantities of the *cis*-conformation²⁴.

Takao and Iwasa²⁵ have made a detailed spectroscopic study of 22 tetrahydroprotoberberines and have derived some valuable conclusions. 13-methyltetrahydroprotoberberines, which have the C₁₃ hydrogen and C₁₄ hydrogen *cis* exist almost exclusively in the *trans*-quinolizidine form. Those in which these two hydrogens have a *trans*-relationship exist almost entirely in the *cis*-quinolizidine form. In the case of compounds which have an oxygen substituent at C₁, the *cis*-quinolizidine form predominates, but there is always some amount of the *trans*-quinolizidine, which decreases with the increasing bulk of the C₁-substituent.

NMR spectroscopy has been of great value in assigning conformation to 13-methyltetrahydroprotoberberines. The chemical shift of the C₁₃ methyl group in compounds with *trans*-fused B/C rings (C₁₃H and C₁₄H *cis*) is between δ 0.90-1.00, while it is at δ 1.40-1.50 in the *cis*-fused B/C ring

compounds (C₁₃H and C₁₄H *trans*). In the spectra of *trans*-fused 9, 10-dioxygenated-13-methyltetrahydroprotoberberines the C₈ protons appear as an AB quartet with a large difference²⁵, in chemical shift, while in the corresponding *cis*-quinolizidine, the shift difference is smaller. Recently Cushman *et al.*²² pointed out that the C₈ proton in the B/C *cis*-fused 10, 11-dioxygenated tetrahydroprotoberberines, the protons at C₈ appeared as two doublets (J=16 Hz) at δ 3.7 and δ 4.2, while a broad singlet corresponding to these protons showed up at δ 3.7 in the *trans*-fused compound.

Pai *et al.*²⁶ carried out a 90 MHz NMR study of several 9, 10- and 10, 11-dioxygenated tetrahydroprotoberberines. They concluded that the C₈ protons are observed as an AB quartet whether the B/C ring fusion was *cis* or *trans* irrespective of the oxygenation pattern. The centre of the AB quartet appears relatively downfield in all cases of *cis*-quinolizidines as compared to the *trans*-quinolizidines by about 0.15-0.20 ppm. In 10, 11-dioxygenated compounds, the signals of the C₈ protons are separated by 0.45-0.48 ppm in the *cis*- and 0.40-0.48 ppm in the *trans*-quinolizidines, while the corresponding values in 9, 10-oxygenated compounds are 0.13-0.18 and 0.55-0.72 ppm. The most consistent and dramatic difference between the *cis*- and *trans*-quinolizidines is seen in the chemical shift of the methyl group at C₁₃. These values range from δ 1.43-1.48 for the *cis* and δ 0.88-0.99 for the *trans*-series, irrespective of the oxygenation pattern.

An unintended route to tetrahydroprotoberberines :

Lastly, brief mention may be made of the formation of tetrahydroprotoberberines during the course of debenzoylation of certain 1-benzyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinolines²⁷. Thus debenzoylation of 1-(3-benzyloxy-6-bromo-4-methoxybenzyl)-6, 7-methylenedioxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (XXX) gave the corresponding hydroxy compound (XXXI) as well as 12-bromo nandinine (XXXII) which could be debrominated to nandinine. Irradiation of the 2-bromo-

3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzyl-6,7-methylenedioxy 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline gave the aporphine (XXXIII) as also the compound XXXII. Although the yield of the tetrahydroprotoberberine is very low, its formation is intriguing. Detailed studies were carried out on both debenylation and photolysis of a variety of 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinolines²⁷ which depict the conditions needed for the formation of the tetrahydroprotoberberines. These are : (a) the nitrogen has to be secondary ; (b) the position adjacent to the benzylic carbon on the potential ring D has to be activated by a suitably positioned hydroxy group. Under photolytic conditions, tetrahydroprotoberberine formation will take place if these conditions are met. However for this to take place under debenylation conditions, a methoxyl or methylenedioxy group has to be present in the structure.

The one-carbon unit furnishing the berberine bridge apparently arises from the methylenedioxy or methoxy group present, under debenylation conditions. The formation of formaldehyde from the methylenedioxy function is easily understood but its formation from methyl halide or methanol released from methoxyl function needs a further oxidation stage and the mechanism is not obvious.

Photolysis of 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline in aqueous acidic medium generated formaldehyde (Chart 7).

An explanation would be a retro-Diels-Alder reaction releasing C₈ of the isoquinoline as formaldehydeimine.

Although the first alkaloid berberine was isolated some 150 years ago, interest in this group of compounds has not abated. There is a large volume of interesting work both as regards synthesis as well as reactions of this class of alkaloids which are being constantly brought out.

In this lecture our attention has been confined to the work carried out at Presidency College, Madras largely under the guidance of Prof. B. R. Pai and Dr. K. Nagarajan. I am grateful to them for valuable help in the preparation of this lecture.

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